

“KIDNEY CARE COMMUNITY” FOR SELF-CARE IN EARLY-STAGE CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE

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Introduction: Chronic kidney disease (CKD) requires long-term management, with treatment success largely depending on patient adherence and self-monitoring. Many patients, however, struggle with consistent medication use and tracking of vital health indicators. Digital tools offer new opportunities to support patients in daily disease management. “Kidney Care Community” is an interactive platform designed to enhance compliance and self-care in CKD. This study evaluates its effectiveness in improving treatment adherence and monitoring behaviors in patients with stage I–III CKD.

Aim: To evaluate the effectiveness of the “Kidney Care Community” interactive platform in improving adherence to treatment and self-monitoring behaviors in individuals diagnosed with stage I–III chronic kidney disease (CKD).

Materials and Methods: A randomized clinical study involved 48 patients (aged 25–60) with CKD stages I–III, divided into two equal groups. The intervention group used the “Kidney Care Community” platform for 4 months, while the control group received standard outpatient care. Intervention participants logged daily health data (blood pressure, weight, medication, symptoms) and received reminders and expert feedback. Treatment adherence was measured using MMAS-8, self-monitoring by the frequency of BP and lab checks, and kidney function by changes in GFR.

Results: The intervention group demonstrated a significant improvement in treatment adherence, with MMAS-8 scores increasing from 5.2 ± 1.1 to 6.8 ± 0.9 ($p < 0.01$), while the control group showed only a slight, non-significant change (5.1 ± 1.0 to 5.3 ± 1.2 ; $p > 0.05$). Self-monitoring activities, such as blood pressure and weight tracking, rose by 35% ($p < 0.05$) in the intervention group, along with reduced BP variability. After four months, GFR declined more slowly in the intervention group (-1.4 mL/min/1.73 m²) than in the control group (-3.2 mL/min/1.73 m²; $p < 0.05$), suggesting delayed disease progression. KDQOL scores improved by an average of 1.8 points ($p < 0.05$), with participants reporting better well-being, confidence in managing their condition, and more active treatment involvement. Moreover, 80% reported enhanced awareness and actively used the platform’s community features for support.

Conclusion: The use of the “Kidney Care Community” interactive service markedly enhances medication adherence and self-care behaviors in patients with CKD. The platform contributes to slowing disease progression and improving quality of life, highlighting the potential benefits of integrating digital health tools into routine CKD care.